

A STUDY ON GOVERNMENT POLICY INITIATIVES TOWARDS SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT WITH REFERENCE TO MUMBAI SUBURBAN AREA

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Abstract

Industrialization becomes very significant for developing countries like India having large number of population. Rapid increase in urbanization and per capita income lead to high rate of municipal solid waste generation. In recent times, E-waste and plastic waste also contribute considerably to total waste stream due to utilization of electronic and other items. These wastes may cause a potential hazard to human health or environment if any of the aspects of solid waste management is not managed effectively. In India, approach towards Solid waste management is still unscientific.

Key Words: *Solid Waste, Hazards, Plastic waste, urbanisation, municipal authorities*

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Introduction

India is having second largest population in the world after China with more than 1.27 billion population contributing 17.6% of world's total population (Official population clock). On the contrary, India is sharing only 5% of world's area accounting 3,185,263 km². Out of total population, 68% lives in rural areas, while 32% lives in urban areas (World Bank, 2014). Urban population is increasing day by day since last few decades. In modern society, industry becomes an essential part. Developing countries like India is in industrialization phase, which also contribute to urbanization. Large number of people are migrating towards city area for better opportunities. Over-population, Rapid industrialization. Uncontrolled urbanization and improved living standards thereby lead to increased rate of per capita waste generation

Solid waste management (SWM) has emerged as one of the most massive development challenges in urban India. Numerous studies indicate that the unsafe disposal of waste generates dangerous gases and leachates, due to microbial decomposition, climate conditions, refuse characteristics and land-filling operations.

Review of Literature

- Banga (2013) reported in her work that participation in solid waste management activities depends on the level of awareness, household income, educational level and gender.

- Adeyemo and Gboyesola (2013) stated that, the attitude of people towards waste management can be affected by their level of knowledge and awareness of waste management. They also reported that homes with waste bins engage more in proper way of storing waste than homes without waste bins.
- Yadav & Mishra (2004) opined that Hygiene starts from home. Our household waste accounts for major amount of solid rubbish. Some are reusable and others non-reusable. All these constitute megatons of municipal wastes. If it is not properly disposed off, the consequences are dangerous
- Al-Khatib et al (2015) and Hilburn (2015) evolved that most communities in developing countries often turn to waste disposal methods that have proven to be destructive to human health and the environment, such as open dumping and burning (or unregulated landfills) because they feel they have no other options to manage their solid waste.

Problem Statement

Household wastes account for major amount of solid rubbish. All the usable and non-reusable waste constitute megatons of municipal waste. If it is not properly disposed off, its consequences are dangerous. There is an urgent need to streamline and sensitize minds of the consumers to the varied problems and concerns related to the environment.

In this regard, it would be worthwhile to know solid waste management behaviour, current situation of the willingness, collection and transfer, residents' mode of solid waste collection, treatment and disposal. With the above mentioned research problem in hand, the study could focus in finalising the research objectives, hypotheses and supporting research methodology.

Research Objectives

1. To study the concept of Solid Waste Management.
2. To study citizens attitude and behaviour towards solid waste management
3. To study citizens' attitude and behaviour towards solid waste management
4. To suggest suitable waste management techniques for sustainable environment growth.

Hypothesis of the Study

There is an influence of citizens' attitude and behaviour towards solid waste management practices.

Research Methodology

The study is based on Primary and Secondary data. Primary data is collected through observation method. The secondary data is collected through magazines government bulletins, websites.

Findings of Study

The Ministry of Environment and Forests (MoEF) is taking care of the issues related to solid waste management together with Central and State Pollution Control Boards. There are various rules framed under Environment Protection Act - 1986 for improving management of solid waste. SWM falls under state list as it is considered as public health and sanitation as per Indian Constitution. Due to its local nature, SWM is the responsibility of Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) (European Business and Technology

Centre).

1. Legislation

- Environment Protection Act – 1986
- Hazardous Waste Management and Handling Rules – 1989
- Manufacturing, Storage and Transportation of Hazardous Waste Rules – 1989 □ Bio-Medical Waste Management and Handling Rules – 1998
- Municipal Solid Waste Management and Handling Rules – 2000 □ Plastic Waste (Management and Handling) Rules – 2011
- E-Waste (Management and Handling) Rules – 2011- 8.

2. Municipal Solid Waste Management and Handling Rules – 2000

A PIL was filed by Almitra H. Patel in Supreme Court based on allegations of failure of MSW management by GOI, State Governments and Local Authorities. The Supreme Court then appointed an Expert committee which submitted its report to Supreme Court on March, 1999. Local authorities were asked to implement the recommendations given by Expert committee. The major recommendations have been included in the Municipal Solid Waste (Management and Handling Rules – 2000) notified by Ministry of Environment and Forest, September 2000. These rules apply to every municipal authority responsible for collection, segregation, storage, transportation, treatment and disposal of municipal solid waste.

3. Responsibility of Municipal Authority

- Every municipal authority shall, within the territorial area of the municipality, be responsible for the implementation of the provisions of these rules, and for any infrastructure development for collection, storage, segregation, transportation, processing and disposal of municipal solid wastes.
- The municipal authority or an operator of a facility shall make an application in Form-I, for grant of authorization for setting up waste processing and disposal facility including landfills from the State Board or the Committee in order to comply with the implementation programme laid down in Schedule I.
- The municipal authority shall comply with these rules as per the implementation schedule laid down in Schedule I. The municipal authority shall furnish its annual report in Form-II, - to the Secretary-incharge of the Department of Urban Development of the concerned State or as the case may be of the Union territory, in case of a metropolitan city; or to the District Magistrate or the Deputy Commissioner concerned in case of all other towns and cities, with a copy to the State Board or the Committee on or before the 30th day of June every year.

4. Responsibility of State Government and The Union Territory

- The Secretary-incharge of the Department of Urban Development of the concerned State or the

Union territory, as the case may be, shall have the overall responsibility for the enforcement of the provisions of these rules in the metropolitan cities.

- The District Magistrate or the Deputy Commissioner of the concerned district shall have the overall responsibility for the enforcement of the provisions of these rules within the territorial limits of their jurisdiction.

5. Responsibility of Pollution Control Boards and Committees

- The State Board or the Committee shall monitor the compliance of the standards regarding ground water, ambient air, leachate quality and the compost quality including incineration standards as specified under Schedules II, III and IV.
- The State Board or the Committee, after the receipt of application from the municipal authority or the operator of a facility in Form I, for grant of authorization for setting up waste processing and disposal facility including landfills, shall examine the proposal taking into consideration the views of other agencies like the State Urban Development Department, the Town and Country Planning Department, Air Port or Air Base Authority, the Ground Water Board or any such other agency prior to issuing the authorization.

Significance of the Study

- The present study is an attempt to assess the awareness and attitude of people towards solid waste management practices. This approach tries to fill deficiencies of the critical issues of waste management which is a serious concern of environmental degradation.
- Planned contribution of solid waste management of consumers is a step towards Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. For successful implementation of waste management, the 3 R's approach-Reduce, Reuse, Recycle would not be possible without contribution of the consumers. People behaviour and attitude is key factor in achieving the targets of different waste management programmes.
- The study would be applied in other geographical are by future researchers.
- The study will be useful to government to draw collaborative action plan through households empowerment sustainable for waste management programmes.

References

- Addaney, M., & Anarfiwaah, O. R. (2015). Critical Issues of Municipal Solid Waste Management in Ghana. JENRM , 2 (1), 30-36.
- Adejobi, O., & Olorunnimbe, R. O. (2012). Challenges of Waste Management and Climate Change in Nigeria: Lagos State Metropolis Experience. African J. Sci. Res. , 7 (1), 346-362.
- Tartiu, V. (2011) Evaluation of attitudes and knowledge regarding municipal waste among students, Case study: Bucharest Academy of Economic studies. J. Economica. Seria Management, 14(1), pp. 263-276
- Yadav, P.R., and Mishra, S.R. (2004) Human Ecology. N. Delhi, Discovery Publishing House

- Karim Ghani WAWA., Rusli IF, Biak DRA, Idris A (2013) An application of the theory of planned behaviour to study the influencing factors of participation in source separation of food waste. *Waste Manag* 33:1276–1281
- Hayami, Y.; Dikshit, A.K.; Mishra, S.N. Waste pickers and collectors in Delhi: Poverty and environment in an urban informal sector. *J. Dev. Stud.* 2006, 42, 41–69. [CrossRef]
- Municipal Corporation of Delhi. Feasibility Study and Master Plan for Optimal Waste Treatment and Disposal for the Entire State of Delhi Based on Public Private Partnership Solutions. Volume 6: Municipal Solid Waste Characterisation Report; Municipal Corporation of Delhi: Delhi, India, 2004